

AN EMPIRICAL EQUATION RELATING EXTINCTION COEFFICIENT WITH FREQUENCY IN AN ABSORPTION BAND

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An empirical equation relating extinction coefficient with frequency in an absorption band has been developed which can be used in all forms of absorption curves and from this the equation of circular dichroism and rotatory dispersion in the region of absorption have been deduced.

It is well known that there is a quantitative relation between absorption, circular dichroism and circular double refraction (optical activity) in optically active absorbing media. Kuhn and Braun (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, 8 B, 281) obtained such a relation which is

$$\alpha = \frac{57.3}{2\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)_{\max}}{\log_{10} e} \cdot \frac{\nu}{\nu_0} \left[e^{-\left(\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta}\right)^2} \int_0^{\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta}} e^{x^2} dx - \frac{\theta}{2(\nu_0 + \nu)} \right]$$

where α is the rotatory contribution of an optically active absorption band, expressed in degrees per cm. column of the solution at frequency ν ; $(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)_{\max}$ is the maximum value of circular dichroism of that band at frequency ν_0 , and the parameter θ is related to the half-width of the experimental curve of circular dichroism of the band by the relation: ν (half-width) = 1.6651 θ . This equation was modified by Lowry and Hudson (*Phil. Trans.*, 1933, A, 232, 117). All these rotatory dispersion equations are based on the absorption equations which represent the absorption curves responsible for optical activity. It is therefore important to determine first of all the mathematical form of absorption curves which can subsequently be used to deduce equations for curves of circular dichroism and rotatory dispersion. The existing equations of absorption by Ketteler-Helmholtz (Lowry, "Optical Rotatory Power," Cambridge, 1935, p 395); by Kuhn (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, 4B, 14; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 26, 293), by Kuhn and Braun (*loc. cit.*) by Lowry and Hudson (*loc. cit.*) and by Bielecki and Henri (*Physikal. Z.*, 1913, 14, 516) cannot be used in all forms of absorption curves and cannot also represent the experimental data satisfactorily. Thus, the equation of Ketteler and Helmholtz

$$\epsilon = \frac{a\lambda^2}{(\lambda^2 - \lambda_m^2)^2 + b^2\lambda^2}$$

represents an absorption curve which is unsymmetrical both with respect to frequencies and to wave-lengths. When plotted on a scale of frequencies, it is steeper on the low-frequency side and, when plotted on a scale of wave-lengths, it is steeper on the short wave-length side. The equation of Kuhn, namely

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_{\max} \cdot \frac{\nu^2 \nu_0^2}{(\nu_0^2 - \nu^2)^2 + \nu^2 \nu_0^2} \approx \epsilon_{\max} \frac{\nu^2}{2(\nu_0 - \nu)^2 + \nu^2}$$

and that of Kuhn and Braun, namely, $\epsilon = \epsilon_{\max} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta}\right)^2}$ represent absorption curves

which are symmetrical on a scale of frequencies. The equation of Lowry and Hudson, namely

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_{\max} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{\lambda - \lambda_0}{\theta}\right)^2}$$

represents curve which is symmetrical when plotted on a scale of wave-lengths, but steeper on the low-frequency side when plotted on a scale of frequencies. Lastly, the equation

$$\epsilon = \alpha \nu e^{-\beta(\nu - \nu_0)^2}$$

of Bielecki and Henri, represents curve which is steeper on the low-frequency side when plotted on a scale of frequencies. In the present communication a new empirical equation has been developed which can be used in all forms of absorption curves, either symmetrical or unsymmetrical on a scale of frequencies or wave-lengths.

For the purpose of analysis of an absorption curve, plotted on a scale of frequencies, we divide the curve into two components, one on the low-frequency side of $\epsilon_{\max}$ and the other on the high-frequency side of $\epsilon_{\max}$, where $\epsilon_{\max}$ is the maximum value of extinction coefficient in the experimental curve corresponding to the frequency ν_0 . The extinction coefficient ϵ , corresponding to any frequency ν on the low-frequency side, can be represented by the equation

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_{\max} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta_1}\right)^2}, \text{ where } \theta_1 = \frac{\nu_0 - \nu_1}{0.8326},$$

ν_1 being the frequency of the point at the experimental curve on the low-frequency side at which ϵ is half $\epsilon_{\max}$. Similarly the extinction coefficient ϵ , corresponding to any frequency ν on the high-frequency side, can be represented by the equation

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_{\max} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{\nu - \nu_2}{\theta_2}\right)^2} \text{ where } \theta_2 = \frac{\nu_2 - \nu_0}{0.8326},$$

ν_2 being the frequency of the point on the high-frequency side at which ϵ is half $\epsilon_{\max}$. The factor 0.8326 ensures that the theoretical curve calculated by the above equations coincides with the experimental curve at the two points ν_1 and ν_2 , as well as ν_0 . If the curve is symmetrical, we have $(\nu_0 - \nu_1) = (\nu_2 - \nu_0)$ so that

$$\theta_1 = \theta_2 = \frac{\nu_0 - \nu_1}{0.8326} = \frac{2(\nu_0 - \nu_1)}{1.6652} = \frac{\nu'}{1.6652} = \theta$$

where ν' is called the half-width of the band.

The absorption equation for a symmetrical curve therefore becomes

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_{\max} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta}\right)^2} \text{ where } \theta = \frac{\nu'}{1.6652}$$

This equation is the same as the equation of Kuhn and Braun which gives a theoretical absorption curve symmetrical on a scale of frequencies. These new equations there-

fore can be used to represent any curve, whether symmetrical or unsymmetrical. For symmetrical curve, the value of θ_1 is equal to θ_2 , while for unsymmetrical curve, they are different. Similar equations hold good when the curve is plotted on a scale of wave-lengths, namely, for longer wave-length side of $\epsilon_{\max}$

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_{\max} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{\lambda - \lambda_1}{\theta_1}\right)^2}$$

where $\theta_1 = \frac{\lambda_1 - \lambda_0}{0.832\theta}$ and for the shorter wave-length side of $\epsilon_{\max}$, $\epsilon = \epsilon_{\max} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{\lambda_0 - \lambda}{\theta_2}\right)^2}$

where $\theta_2 = \frac{\lambda_0 - \lambda_2}{0.832\theta}$, λ_1 and λ_2 being the wave-lengths at which ϵ is half $\epsilon_{\max}$.

The applicability of these new absorption equations has been tested in the case of unsymmetrical absorption curves of acetone in water and alcohol, and the absorption curve of acetaldehyde in water studied by Bielecki and Henri (*loc. cit.*).

Bielecki and Henri determined the molecular extinction coefficient of pure acetone, solutions of acetone in water and alcohol and of solutions of acetic acid and acetaldehyde in water for different wave-lengths in the ultraviolet region. By applying the Ketteler and Helmholtz equation, they found a discrepancy between the observed extinction coefficient and the theoretical values. They therefore proposed the exponential formula,

$$\epsilon = a\nu e^{-\beta(\nu - \nu_0)^2}$$

which represented the experimental data better than the Ketteler-Helmholtz equation. It is found that a still better agreement is obtained by applying the new equations given above. The observed values and the theoretical values calculated according to all these three equations are tabulated in Tables I, II and III.

TABLE I

Absorption of acetone in water.

Equation of Ketteler and Helmholtz : $a = 1.43 \times 10^4$; $g^2 = 7.8 \times 10^4$; $\lambda_m = 2655\text{\AA}$.

Equation of Bielecki & Henri : $a = 1.57 \times 10^{-3}$; $\beta = 1.18 \times 10^{-4}$; $\nu_0 = 1133$.

Kar's equation : $\epsilon_{\max} = 17.8$; $\nu_1 \times 10^{-14} = 11.33$; $\nu_2 \times 10^{-14} = 10.56$;

$\theta_1 \times 10^{-14} = 0.9249$; $\theta_2 \times 10^{-14} = 12.3$; $\theta_3 \times 10^{-14} = 1.165$.

λ	ϵ obs.	ϵ calc. (K & H)	ϵ calc. (B & H)	ϵ calc. (Kar)	λ	ϵ obs.	ϵ calc. (K & H)	ϵ calc. (B & H)	ϵ calc. (Kar)
2144	0.54	1.03	0.0053	0.10	2705	16.2	16.3	16.3	16.64
2265	2.16	1.80*	0.28*	1.21	2744	14.0	13.16*	14.21*	14.77
2307	3.2	2.24	0.77	2.28	2815	10.8	8.4	9.87	10.37
2352	4.6	2.90*	1.79*	3.95	2852	8.1	6.46	7.64	8.26
2398	7.0	3.8	3.82	6.38	2892	5.5	5.02*	5.49*	6.08
2444	9.4	5.26*	6.80*	9.29	2928	4.04	4.10	4.08	4.44
2468	10.8	6.25*	8.64*	10.65	2960	2.7	3.46*	2.99*	3.40
2539	14.0	10.7	14.0	15.02	2981	2.16	3.13	2.70	2.78
2575	16.2	13.70*	16.21*	16.51	3001	1.62	2.84	1.90	2.23
2648	17.8	18.3	17.8	17.8	3040	1.08	2.40	1.03	1.46

*These values have been calculated by us.

TABLE II

*Absorption of acetone in alcohol.*Equation of Beilecki & Henri : $\alpha = 1.42 \times 10^{-2}$; $\beta = 1.525 \times 10^{-4}$; $\nu_0 = 1109$.Kar's equation : $\epsilon_{\max} = 15.8$; $\nu_0 \times 10^{-14} = 11.09$; $\nu_1 \times 10^{-14} = 10.28$; $\theta_1 \times 10^{-14} = 0.9729$; $\nu_2 \times 10^{-14} = 11.94$; $\theta_2 \times 10^{-14} = 1.021$.

λ .	ϵ obs.	ϵ calc. (K & H)	ϵ calc. (B & H)	ϵ calc. (Kar)	λ .	ϵ obs.	ϵ calc. (K & H)	ϵ calc. (K & H)	ϵ calc. (Kar)
2288	1.4	2.42	0.087	0.315	2706	15.8	15.8	15.8	15.8
2331	2.16	2.93	0.154*	0.79	2770	14.0	14.9	3.98	14.63
2382	2.5	3.72	0.58*	1.83	2845	10.8	11.57	9.67	11.48
2405	4.2	4.17	1.11	2.55	2981	5.5	6.25	2.94*	5.27
2488	7.0	6.41	4.09*	6.41	3347	3.2	4.71	1.35	3.07
2581	10.80	10.5	12.14	12.07	3120	1.4	3.57	0.48	1.58
2648	14.0	14.0	14.84	14.95	3280	0.054	2.16	0.042	0.29

*Values calculated by us.

TABLE III

Absorption of acetaldehyde in water. $\epsilon_{\max} = 6.35$; $\nu_0 \times 10^{-14} = 10.85$; $\nu_1 \times 10^{-14} = 10.04$; $\theta_1 \times 10^{-14} = 0.9729$; $\nu_2 \times 10^{-14} = 11.79$; $\theta_2 \times 10^{-14} = 1.129$.

λ .	ϵ obs.	ϵ calc. (B & H)	ϵ calc. (Kar)	λ .	ϵ obs.	ϵ calc. (B & H)	ϵ calc. (Kar)
2393	1.30	0.22	0.69	2892	5.2	4.57	4.98
2460	1.8	0.78	1.52	2926	4.4	3.86	4.34
2490	2.16	1.04	1.86	2981	3.6	2.73	3.34
2525	2.75	1.9	2.76	3001	2.8	2.41	2.95
2550	3.51	2.85	3.27	3047	2.3	1.66	2.18
2620	4.3	4.3	4.79	3079	1.4	1.32	1.74
2630	4.6	4.54	5.01	3100	1.3	1.05	1.49
2684	5.4	5.72	5.83	3140	0.70	0.70	1.08
				3200	0.27	0.37	0.64

Similar to the new absorption equation, the equation of circular dichroism will be

$$(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r) = (\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)_{\max} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta_1}\right)^2} \text{ for frequencies less than } \nu_0, \text{ and}$$

$$(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r) = (\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)_{\max} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{\nu - \nu_0}{\theta_2}\right)^2} \text{ for frequencies greater than } \nu_0,$$

where ν_0 is the frequency corresponding to maximum circular dichroism $(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)_{\max}$ and $\theta_1 = \frac{\nu_0 - \nu_1}{0.8326}$ and $\theta_2 = \frac{\nu_2 - \nu_0}{0.8326}$; ν_1 and ν_2 are the frequencies at which $(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)$ is halfthe maximum value in the experimental curve of circular dichroism. If $(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)$ is

$$\text{plotted against } \lambda, \text{ the equations become } (\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r) = (\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)_{\max} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{\lambda - \lambda_0}{\theta_1}\right)^2} \text{ for wave-lengths}$$

greater than λ_0 , and $(\epsilon_i - \epsilon_r) = (\epsilon_i - \epsilon_r)_{\max} e^{-\left(\frac{\lambda_0 - \lambda}{\theta_1}\right)^2}$ for wave-lengths less than λ_0 , θ_1 being equal to $\frac{\lambda_1 - \lambda_0}{0.8326}$ and $\theta_2 = \frac{\lambda_0 - \lambda_2}{0.8326}$.

The partial rotation contributed by an optically active absorption band in the region of absorption α outside it can therefore be obtained by the equations:

$$\alpha = \frac{57.3}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{(\epsilon_i - \epsilon_r)_{\max}}{\log_{10} e} \frac{\nu}{\nu_0} \left[e^{-\left(\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta_1}\right)^2} \int_0^{\nu_0 - \nu} e^{x^2} dx - \frac{\theta_1}{2(\nu_0 + \nu)} \right]$$

for frequencies less than ν_0 , and

$$\alpha = -\frac{57.3}{2\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{(\epsilon_i - \epsilon_r)_{\max}}{\log_{10} e} \frac{\nu}{\nu_0} \left[e^{-\left(\frac{\nu - \nu_0}{\theta_1}\right)^2} \int_0^{\nu - \nu_0} e^{x^2} dx + \frac{\theta_2}{2(\nu_0 + \nu)} \right]$$

for frequencies greater than ν_0 .

$(\epsilon_i - \epsilon_r)_{\max}$, ν_0 , θ_1 and θ_2 have the same significance and values as in the curve of circular dichroism of the optically active absorption band and α is the rotatory contribution expressed in degrees per cm. column of the solution.

Expressed in wave-lengths,

$$\alpha = \frac{57.3}{2\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{(\epsilon_i - \epsilon_r)_{\max}}{\log_{10} e} \frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda} \left[e^{-\left(\frac{\lambda - \lambda_0}{\theta_1}\right)^2} \int_0^{\lambda - \lambda_0} e^{x^2} dx + \frac{\theta_1}{2(\lambda + \lambda_0)} \right]$$

for wave-lengths greater than λ_0 , and

$$\alpha = -\frac{57.3}{2\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{(\epsilon_i - \epsilon_r)_{\max}}{\log_{10} e} \frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda} \left[e^{-\left(\frac{\lambda_0 - \lambda}{\theta_1}\right)^2} \int_0^{\lambda_0 - \lambda} e^{x^2} dx - \frac{\theta_2}{2(\lambda + \lambda_0)} \right]$$

for wave-lengths less than λ_0 .

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